

BRAIN AND MENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract: Currently, a lot of research is being conducted in a state that combines the fields of medicine and psychology. In the article, we will focus on the problems of the brain and psyche, which are important elements of these two areas.

Key words: brain, psyche, neurological disorder, comorbidity, phobia, unconsciousness, expression of thoughts, nature of consciousness.

Along with neurological disorders, mental and emotional disorders are also observed after brain injuries. These disorders depend on the severity, type, age of the patient, the presence of concomitant diseases, and other similar factors. Brain injury or concussion is often observed in brain injuries. In such cases, most patients lose consciousness, and how deep it is depends on the level of injury. Usually, when the patient regains consciousness, memory disturbances of various forms and degrees are observed.

In many cases, a strong phobia develops after brain injuries. For example, patients who have been injured in a car accident are afraid to go out, cross pedestrian areas, or even go somewhere in motor vehicles, or suffer from a fear of death. [6, 56]

According to psychologists, along with the maturation of a human child, many functions are characterized by the fact that they get out of the control of the mind and acquire an automatic character. For example, the first time we sit in a car, the first time we take a picture, almost all our actions are under the strict control of the mind. Over time, we begin to perform many actions unconsciously, without realizing it. Such a situation does not deny the fact that consciousness actively interferes in various spheres and directions of human activity, i.e. it can take control over the activity. On the one

hand, the strengthening of behavior into the field of unconsciousness serves to relieve the "absence" of consciousness, on the other hand, it creates an opportunity to focus the main power, energy, "attention" of consciousness on actions and processes that are important for human life. [5, 90]

The unconscious also includes such phenomena as intuition, imagination, instinct and intuition, which are outside the control of the mind. Considering these features, unconsciousness can be said to be a natural condition for the existence and development of consciousness. Subconscious phenomena are also an important part of mental processes. According to Z. Freud, they are the boundary between unconsciousness and consciousness.

It can be said that the proverb "There is a story under a word, and a cup under a cup" expresses the characteristics of the subconscious. Because in any of our activities there are situations that are not important for us at the same time. However, this does not mean that they are left out of observation and control. When they acquire a significant character for us, they can move from the subconscious to the conscious sphere. For example, when going somewhere, one moves towards the goal, but also observes and remembers other things and events encountered on the way. Based on this, it can be said that the subconscious has the qualities of acting as a special monitor of the conscious activity of a person, a sensor when necessary. [3, 159]

According to the results of some studies, the results achieved in the field of science are doubling every ten years, and information acquisition is doubling every 3-4 years. In such a situation, the question of whether the human mind and its memory can absorb this information is being discussed. In the recent past, when the flow of new knowledge and information was not so strong, a diligent person could master the main results of human knowledge. Today, several million books are published annually in various fields of science. According to calculations, even when a person tries to study the latest literature, for every page he reads, there are ten thousand unread pages. [1, 63]

The fact that people have not had time to physically read most of the new books that have appeared is just one of the consequences of the "information explosion". There is another aspect of the problem, which is the moral obsolescence of the knowledge and information accumulated by a person, becoming unnecessary. The rate of such wear and tear is accelerating. For example, opinions are expressed that this process takes six to seven years in the field of higher education, and one year in the field of computer technology. This means that if it has been seven years since you graduated from a higher education institution, most of the knowledge you received at that time does not meet today's requirements. In such conditions, keeping people's knowledge at a high level requires constant attention and work on themselves.

Otherwise, even a specialist who graduated from an educational institution with the highest results may soon become illiterate. [2, 74]

In general, understanding the essence of consciousness, that it is a natural result of the evolution of the universe, and the scientific interpretation of the processes connected with it make it possible to understand the unity of the universe and man. At the same time, understanding the essence of consciousness opens the way to a deeper understanding of issues such as the identity of a person, the purpose of life, the meaning of life. This shows that consciousness and issues related to it are of practical importance.

Reference:

1. Tolipov U., Usmanbayeva M. *Pedagogik texnologiya:nazariya va amaliyot.*-T.: "Fan". 2005.
2. Iqboljon O'g'li, Tojimamatov Jamshidbek, and Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher o'g'li. "THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 9.3 (2022): 4-7.
3. Khakimov, Mukhammad Khodjakhonovich, and Azimjon Latifjon ugli Melikuziev. "The History of Paralinguistic Researches." *International Journal of Culture and Modernity* 13 (2022): 90-95.
4. Akhmedov, A., and O. Egamberdiyev. "PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS." *Science and innovation* 1. B4 (2022): 136-138.
5. Alisher o'g'li, Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh. "Issues of Retraining and Professional Development of Pedagogical Personnel." *The Peerian Journal* 5 (2022): 192-194.
6. Tojimamatov, Jamshidbek, and Oyatillokh Egamberdiyev. "THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON." *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research* 2.5 (2022): 470-473.
7. Khakimov, M. K., & ugli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). The History of Paralinguistic Researches. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 13, 90-95.
8. ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126-128.
9. Vasila Karimova. *Salomatlik psixologiyasi.* -T .: 2005.
10. Визел Т.Г. *Основы нейропсихологии.* -М .: 2000.